

THE ROLE OF THE 6-MINUTE ENGLISH PODCASTS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *The article discusses about the role of 6-minute English in mastering the English language intensively by providing relevant examples and also shows the various methods of the utilization 6-minute English in enriching vocabulary, including idioms, collocations, and phrasal verbs. Furthermore, it reveals the huge importance of 6-minute English in enhancement of pronunciation of language learners.*

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Listening has an essential role in learning as it is one of the four main skills in language acquisition. Although the other skills such as reading, speaking and writing are paramount to improve language proficiency, listening contributes primarily for language expertise. Listening awakens awareness of the language as it is a receptive skill that first develops in a human being. Learning to listen to the target language improves language ability. The sound, rhythm, intonation, and stress of the language can only be perfectly adapted through listening. To understand the nuances in a particular language, one must be able to listen. As we get to understand spoken language by listening it is easier to improve the other skills and gain confidence. Other than being the primary form of communication, listening helps the language learner to understand the beauty of the language. Especially in terms of communicative language teaching it is said that the basis for communicative competence is listening as it provides the aural input and enables learners to interact in spoken communication and hence language learning largely depends on listening. Thus, listening forms the concrete basis for the complete language proficiency and here, the role of BBC podcasts plays a key role in the improvement of learning English language, particularly using the 6-minute English podcasts.

Listening is the most significant part of communication as it is pivotal in providing a substantial and meaningful response. Especially in learning a language for communicative purpose, listening plays a vital role, as it helps the language learner to acquire pronunciation, word stress, vocabulary, and syntax and the comprehension of messages conveyed can be based solely on tone of voice, pitch and accent; and it is only possible when we listen. Without understanding input appropriately, learning simply cannot get any improvement. In addition, without listening skill, no communication can be achieved [1].

Also, every study conducted regarding the language skills acquisition has proved that when we communicate, we gain 45% of language competence from listening, 30% - from speaking, 15% - from reading and 10% - from writing. With the highest percentage of involvement in the exchange of information in effective communication, listening has to be considered a language forerunner. Listening, unlike the other language skills, is felt comparatively much difficult by the

learners, as it has all its interrelated sub-skills such as receiving, understanding, remembering, evaluating, and responding. But with the advent of communicative language-teaching and the focus on proficiency, the learning and teaching of listening started to receive more attention. However, listening is not yet fully integrated into the curriculum and needs to be given more attention in a language learning setting. Podcasts should be integrated with language teaching to support quality language learning and language acquisition. In today's modern era, English listening skills can be practiced at any time, in any place, and in various ways. This is largely due to platforms like Spotify, digital music, podcasts, and video streaming services, which offer content from artists worldwide (Nisa, Izzah, & Hadi 2022)[2]. These platforms offer a wide range of content, providing ample opportunities to practice listening in various contexts. Podcasts, in particular, are an effective tool for improving listening comprehension because they offer flexibility and convenience, allowing learners to practice anywhere and anytime. According to Jovanović (2021)[3], the term podcast combines "pod" from iPod, a popular MP3 player, and "broadcasting." Despite the name originating from iPod, it is not necessary to own an iPod to listen to podcasts; they can be accessed on computers, mobile devices, or other MP3 players. This view is supported by Indahsari (2020)[4], who explained that podcasts are distributed via the internet and can be played on mobile devices or personal computers (PCs). As long as there is internet access, one can listen to podcasts without needing an iPod.

However, singling out the authentic listening material of English language is always considered a huge problem for the learners who are willing to improve their listening skills. According to Kelly, Offner & Vorland (2002)[5], authentic materials are important media, which can be used to focus on between classroom and the real world. Authentic materials aid to give inspiration the learners to study the language, and they will feel that they are learning the real language (Guariento & Morely, 2001)[6]. Underwood (1989)[7] said that a far more real act of communication is heard by the learners by using authentic materials. The learners are given a real representation speech with hesitation, false starts and mistakes which will help the learner to master with the real-life speech when they meet it in other situation or the teaching-learning process. Hence, the 6-minute English can be the primary source of authentic materials due to the various reasons:

These podcasts are prepared by the specialists of target language which provides the essential ingredients for learners to improve listening competence.

Students can both expand their vocabulary and improve their pronunciation using the 6-minute English on a daily basis.

Their availability on the internet is likely to make contribution to the learners who are searching for authentic material.

It is also believed that the 6-minute English will help learners to enrich their vocabulary skills owing to the structure of the 6-minute English which means while listening these authentic materials learners automatically copy these words. Furthermore, the 6-minute podcasts can help in various ways, podcasts can play a significant and versatile role in language acquisition, offering numerous benefits to learners across various levels.

Here are some key ways in which podcasts contribute to language learning:

Exposure to Authentic Language

Podcasts provide exposure to natural, conversational language that is often spoken by native speakers. This includes: -Colloquialisms and idiomatic expressions: Learners hear how language is used in informal settings, which is often very different from textbook language.

Accents and dialects: Podcasts may feature a range of speakers from different regions, allowing learners to hear diverse accents and regional variations, helping them develop better listening comprehension.

Improved Listening Skills

Listening comprehension is crucial for language learning, and podcasts are a great tool for this: Variety of content: There is a wide array of topics, from news to storytelling, to specialized subjects like business or technology. This variety helps learners practice understanding language in different contexts.

Listening at your own pace and learners can pause, rewind, and replay parts of podcasts to improve understanding, allowing them to work through difficult passages at their own speed.

Cultural Context and Insights

Podcasts often delve into cultural contexts, providing learners with an understanding of the culture behind the language.

This can help: Contextual understanding - Language is shaped by culture, so listening to podcasts helps learners understand how language is used in various social and cultural situations. Cultural references - Learners can pick up on cultural references, jokes, and societal norms that they may not encounter in more traditional language lessons.

Pronunciation and Intonation Practice

Regular exposure to spoken language through podcasts allows learners to: Imitate native pronunciation: Hearing native speakers pronounce words and phrases correctly can help learners improve their own pronunciation.

Master intonation and rhythm: Intonation (the rise and fall of pitch) and rhythm are crucial elements of natural speech. By mimicking the speech patterns in podcasts, learners can become more fluent and sounder more natural in their own speech.

Vocabulary Acquisition

Podcasts offer the opportunity to hear a wide range of vocabulary, including both everyday words and more specialized terms:

Active learning: Learners can make note of new words and phrases they hear and look them up, expanding their vocabulary.

Repetition: Common words and phrases are often repeated across episodes, which can help reinforce vocabulary and make it stick.

Improved Grammar

While podcasts are typically more conversational, they still feature correct grammar, allowing learners to hear grammar in context:

Contextual grammar learning: Learners can hear grammatical structures used naturally within conversations, helping them internalize grammar patterns rather than memorizing rules in isolation.

Grammar in context: Unlike textbooks that often present isolated sentences, podcasts show how grammar operates in natural, flowing speech, making it easier to understand how and when to use different grammatical forms.

Convenient, On-the-Go Learning

Podcasts are highly portable and can be consumed while multitasking, making them an excellent tool for language learners with busy lifestyles:

Learning during daily activities: Learners can listen to podcasts during commutes, exercise, or household chores, maximizing learning time.

Flexibility: There's no set schedule for podcast listening, so learners can choose the time and pace that works best for them.

Engagement and Motivation

Podcasts often feature interesting and engaging content, which can help maintain a learner's motivation:

Storytelling and interviews: Many podcasts feature compelling stories or interviews with interesting guests, keeping learners engaged and curious.

Variety and novelty: The diverse range of topics can cater to different interests, ensuring that learners stay motivated and excited to continue practicing the language.

Accessibility of Content

There is an abundance of podcasts available for language learners at all levels:

Targeted podcasts: There are podcasts specifically designed for language learners, with slower speech, clearer pronunciation, and simplified vocabulary.

Language immersion: For more advanced learners, podcasts in the target language can provide a form of immersive listening, helping them gain fluency and proficiency in the language.

To conclude, the 6-minute English podcasts are a dynamic and accessible tool for language learners, providing authentic exposure to spoken language, diverse content, and cultural insights. With consistent and active engagement, learners can improve their listening, speaking, vocabulary, and even grammar skills. Podcasts complement other forms of language study and can be used at any stage of the learning process, from beginner to advanced.

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